

METHODS OF TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract:

The aim of this article is to provide and explain the appropriate way of teaching to young school teachers and understand the characteristics of the different methods used in teaching a foreign language to avoid difficulties in teaching a foreign language and to achieve good results taking into account the individual needs of young learners.

Key words: audio-lingualism, Communicative approach, Task-based learning, Humanistic teaching, the Natural.

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Introduction

In recent years young learners has been interesting in learning English by this way requirement in English language is rising. Currently English is offered in primary and even in pre-school education. There are a lot of opportunities that English language offers to young learners.

- Learning English enhances cognitive abilities. Studies have shown that bilingual children often demonstrate superior cognitive abilities including a better understanding of shapes and patterns.

- Global language is English.

- Improves native language skills. Learning English can also enhance your skills in your native language.

- Learning language improves Children memory, thinking, perception, imagination. In this article we will be aware of Methods of teaching language

Methods and materials

According to Kuziev Sarvarbek (published in November 21,2020) Task-Based learning (TBL) is a lesson structure a method of sequencing activities in your lesson.[1] This method is essential for teaching foreign languages nowadays because in task-based learning students are free to use a range different communicative language skills that are important in learning and understanding a new language.[2] So in this way TBL helps students to improve their language skills Secondly one of the popular methods of nowadays is Total physical response (TPR) method. In the works of Aprilia Riyana (published in 2026) Total physical response is one of an alternative good method for teaching English for young learners to memorize some commands or some vocabularies easily through use their physical. According to Mubin Muradovich Raximov Muradovich, Raximov Mubin (published in 2021) Presentation Practice-Production (PPP) - The PPP method could be characterized as a common-sense approach to teaching as it consists of 3 stages that most people who have learnt how to do anything will be familiar with. • The first stage is the presentation of an aspect of language in a context that students are familiar with, much the

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same way that a swimming instructor would demonstrate a stroke outside the pool to beginners. • The second stage is practice, where students will be given an activity that gives them plenty of opportunities to practice the new aspect of language and become familiar with it whilst receiving limited and appropriate assistance from the teacher. To continue with the analogy, the swimming instructor allowing the children to rehearse the stroke in the pool whilst being close enough to give any support required and plenty of encouragement.[4] The final stage is a production where the students will use the language in context, in an activity set up by the teacher who will be giving minimal assistance, like the swimming instructor allowing his young charges to take their first few tentative strokes on their own.

Proverbs-English proverbs can be used as an alternative to having a lead-in activity. Webster defines a proverb as a short, traditional saying that expresses some obvious truth or similar experiences. Proverbs have been used as teaching tools for centuries to teach moral values and social skills. They may deal with mind, wisdom, experience, learning, and authority. They are indeed effective devices to communicate wisdom and knowledge about human nature and the world at large. [5] Proverbs contain truth in few words that relate to everyday life having a universal value, and they can be remembered easily.

Considering the good values of proverbs, a teacher may use proverbs to teach English as a foreign language as a lead-in activity before teaching language skills. [6] It is a good way to consolidate the learning of vocabulary, grammar, sentence patterns, moral values, and the like.

Conclusion

TBL is a form of group learning where you are able to develop skills such as complex problem-solving critical thinking, collaboration and time management. It also allows you to learn about the importance of teamwork and accountability which is highly regarded in the workforce. Total physical response (TPar) as it is popularly known is a language learning method that has body movement and language acquisition at its core solving the body, singing dancing all work very well in this method as it helps the learner cement the action and the meaning with its association in their heads.

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